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UNDERSTANDING DIGITAL CONSUMER CULTURE: THE ROLE OF E-SERVICE RECOVERY, E-SATISFACTION, AND E-LOYALTY IN THE PHILIPPINES E-RETAIL PLATFORMS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of e-service recovery on e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in the setting of e-retail consumers in the Philippines, exploring the mediating function of e-satisfaction in the development of consumeristic behavior in the digital arena. This study specifically aimed to examine the direct effects of e-service recovery on e-satisfaction and e-loyalty, the direct effects of e-satisfaction on e-loyalty, and the mediating role of e-satisfaction in the relationship between e-service recovery and e-loyalty. The research adopted a quantitative descriptive-explanatory research methodology. A total of 405 qualified internet buyers were selected according to the established criteria. Data analysis was done by Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4. The findings show that e-service recovery strongly affects e-loyalty and e-satisfaction whereas e-satisfaction is the most influential factor for e-loyalty. E-satisfaction was also found to strongly moderate the link between e-service recovery and e-loyalty. This result can immediately contribute to a realization that successful recovery techniques improve customer satisfaction which will lead to loyalty and encourage long-term participation with a digital platform. Conclusions reveal that e-service recovery and e-satisfaction are important contributors to customer retention and loyalty in an e-retail environment. This provides insights for e-retail platforms to develop digital service systems and customer experience strategies.

KEYWORDS: E-Service Recovery, E-Satisfaction, E-Loyalty, Digital Consumer Behaviour, E-Retail Platforms, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, Service Recovery, Digital Commerce.

1. INTRODUCTION

Online trade in the Philippine is now making the Filipinos move toward a digital end-consumer culture with a national retail e-commerce growth rate of 25.9% for the fiscal year 2022, edging the first on the growth rate list worldwide. Behind this success was a gigantic engaged digital population of 33.8 million active people shopping on the web and fairly high social media interaction that tends to shape buying action and establish consumer expectations (E-Commerce Evolution in Asia and the Pacific, 2023; Mendoza, 2021; Fang et al., 2022). Yet, all of these added challenges to service failure in terms of delivery bottlenecks, payment irregularities and occasional product mismatches, thereby proving that there is a need for operational improvement in a tough marketplace (Anwar & Ozuem, 2022; Sousa & Voss, 2009; Kim & Kandampully, 2011).

The effects of failure recovery experiences on customer satisfaction and continuous digital engagement are essential because unattended service recovery experiences undermine platform attractions and ruin long term customer relationships. Previous research has taken a service recovery point of view which was discussed under justice theoretical thoughts, digital service quality paradigms such as E-Recovery Service Quality (E-RecS-QUAL) involving responsiveness, fairness, recovery outcomes, and communication. The evaluations reflect customers' perceptions of responsiveness, fairness, service recovery processes, and the outcomes of service failures. Due to recent ethical understanding of recovery; it is established that great recovery does not only survive the problem, but rebuild the service recovery trust, emotional security, and customer satisfaction; then to form e-loyalty in the long run.

Currently, there are only limited empirical work on the mediating role of e-satisfaction in the relationship between e-service recovery and e-loyalty available in the Philippines online market, especially the conversion of recovery experiences into long-term loyalty amidst specific digital behaviours and cultural expectations of Filipino consumer. In response, this study investigates the influence of e-service recovery, e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in building digital consumer culture in Philippine e-retail platforms. From a systems view, e-service recovery is proposed as an important platform feature, e-satisfaction as a user-centric evaluative process and e-loyalty as a long-term behavioural consequence of continuous digital interaction. This study provides context-specific insights for developing more resilient, responsive, and consumer-centric e-commerce environments by

expounding the mediating role of e-satisfaction and contextualizing the analysis within the evolving digital consumer culture of the Philippines. This study sought to: (1) determine the direct effect of e-service recovery to e-loyalty of online shoppers in Philippine e-retail platforms; (2) examine the direct effect of e-service recovery to e-satisfaction of online shoppers in digitally mediated retail environments; (3) investigate the direct effect of e-satisfaction to e-loyalty of online shoppers as an indicator of continued digital consumer engagement; and (4) analyze the mediating effect of e-satisfaction in the relationship between e-service recovery and e-loyalty of online shoppers in the digital marketplace of the Philippines.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concepts of E-Service Recovery. E-service recovery has become an important feature of the current digital consumer culture, influencing how online platforms deal with service failures and affect customer perceptions, experiences, and long-term behavioral commitment. It covers the strategic activities taken by enterprises to correct service failures in digital environments, not just to limit unpleasant experiences but also to repair trust, regain confidence, and improve consumer-platform interactions (Syafriani & Hidayah, 2025). In digital markets, recovery mechanisms function as organizational responses to establish fairness, care, and accountability, with principles of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice forming the foundation to evaluate post-recovery decisions and satisfaction outcomes (Phan et al., 2020). As the digital environment revolutionize, service recovery becomes more difficult with challenges like late delivery, unsecured payments, data privacy issues, technical failures that influence customer trust and necessitate responsive, adaptable recovery mechanisms for the mobile-first and hyper-connected digital lifestyle (Zhu et al., 2021; Liao et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024).

From the consumer culture perspective, perceived justice has a strong connection on the effectiveness of e-service recovery, because customers not only consider the tangible outcomes they receive, but also the fairness of the recovery procedures and the quality of the interpersonal communication during the recovery process (Komunda & Osarenkhoe, 2023; Akarsu et al., 2022). Previous research suggests that when monetary and non-monetary compensation are accompanied by prompt, transparent and sympathetic replies, customer satisfaction after recovery is much enhanced and continuing

consumption is encouraged (Foroudi et al., 2024; Zhu & Park, 2022). In addition, perceived justice theory implies that consumers rate the outcome of the recovery in terms of time, effort, and emotional energy put in and fairness plays a vital role in satisfaction and sustained participation (Gani et al., 2024; Han et al., 2023). Therefore, e-service recovery is not only a solution for operational failure but also a cultural signal for platform reliability, ethical responsibility and consumer-oriented digital engagement in dynamic online marketplaces.

Concepts of E-Satisfaction. This is an important part of digital consumer culture since it assesses how consumers think and feel about their online platform experiences, especially after they experience service recovery. The satisfaction of digital commerce customers is based on how fair recovery processes appear to them, which in turn affects their decision to make repeat purchases and continue using the platform and their overall commitment to the company (Tahir, 2021). The relationships between these two factors become increasingly significant as online services strive to suit customers' needs for instant access, easy procedures and transparent information. The organization successfully generates good perceptions of fairness by its fast issue resolution process and honest communication methods and reasonable treatment of consumers (Aguilar-Rojas et al., 2024; Sarılgan & Yücel, 2024). Satisfaction now reflects a wider view of how consumers see value, fairness and responsiveness within digital service ecosystems, not just transactional fulfillment.

E-satisfaction recovery requires two main elements because operational issues need resolution together with recovery methods that focus on consumer needs and handle emotional situations. The two elements of recovery which include distributive fairness and procedural fairness create separate effects that impact both customer satisfaction and their purchasing decisions after shopping. Interactional justice across differing interaction cues has a moderating role in the development of satisfactory attitudes and intentions to re-patronize in this kind of environment (Lu & Sagman, 2005; Qiang, 2003). If properly carried out, recovery operations may improve customers' perceptions by promoting fairness, trust, and reciprocity, which can lead to positive word-of-mouth, repeat purchases, and stronger customer loyalty. (Kim & Ha, 2003; Chokpiriyawat & Siriyota, 2004; Umar, 2002). Therefore, e-satisfaction is both a consequence of service recovery and an important cultural marker of loyalty, trust and ongoing

participation in digital marketplaces (Arifin et al., 2023; Costa & Rodrigues, 2023).

Concepts of E-Loyalty. E-loyalty is a fundamental composition of digital culture of consumers, which embedded into the willingness of customers to continue transactions, purchase, and advertise a particular online platform, even though several competitor platforms are claimed to be present. Therefore, loyalty in digital markets is indicated not only by repeat buying behavior, continued engagements in the platform, positive word-of-mouth, and strong psychological attachment and trust in consumers, all of which signify strong relationships with digital brands or a service environment. Research also argues that the quality of e-service recovery greatly influences e-loyalty. Beyond resolving transaction issues, effective recovery efforts such as quick responses, sincere apologies, and appropriate compensation help build trust and create positive customer perceptions, leading to long-term consumer loyalty (Dhaniswara et al., 2023; Tengilimoğlu, 2025). Hence, the concept of e-loyalty extends beyond repeat purchases because it exists within a wider system that includes digital trust, ongoing relationships, and consumer connections to platforms.

The digital platforms maintain e-loyalty through their ability to provide users with enjoyable experiences that users consider trustworthy and which operate without interruptions. The combination of e-service quality and successful complaint handling results in higher customer satisfaction which subsequently drives customer loyalty together with extended time on the platform (Indrawati et al., 2024; Ashiq & Hussain, 2023). Online businesses in competitive markets need to provide transparent and responsive services together with exceptional digital experiences in order to meet customer needs. This approach will result in continuous business from current customers who will also recommend the business to others (Al-Mu'ani et al., 2024; Yusnara & Soepatini, 2023; Sadiq et al., 2022). In this line of thinking, satisfaction is an important mediating factor that transforms positive service encounters into lasting loyalty, trust, and commitment; therefore e-loyalty is so much more than mere retention strategy; it is a indicator to committed digital relationships that are built on fulfilled expectations, equity, and reasonable platform interactions (Lim et al., 2025; Kurniadi & Rana, 2023).

Mediating Role of E-Satisfaction on the Effects of E-Service Recovery on E-Loyalty. E-satisfaction acts as a potential mediator in the interaction among

e-service recovery, as well as e-loyalty. E-satisfaction is the key psychological and behaviorally generated mechanism in the digital consumer culture, which is established through the relational conversion of consumer recovery. E-satisfaction is an essentially cognitive evaluation and emotional reaction that emerges from its judgment of the degree to which the consumer's expectations about online service experience have been fulfilled or surpassed, particularly following service failure and recovery efforts (Sihombing et al., 2023). When digital platforms provide appropriate and highly customer-oriented recovery services following disruptions, they often elicit positive post-failure evaluations that help in restoring trust, increasing attachment, and motivating further engagement, repeat purchases, and everlasting loyalty (Jedoy, 2024). In this way, e-satisfaction is not simply a result of service recovery but a transformative intervening variable that turns operational recovery efforts into significant long-term relationship value.

The mediating role of e-satisfaction is particularly important because if service recovery experience is not perceived by the consumers as being truly acceptable, then loyalty may not be sustained by service recovery alone. Loyalty is considered fragile when resolutions are perceived as insufficient, delayed, or unfair. However, perceptions of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice enhance satisfaction and, therefore, affect the continued engagement of the platform (Utami et al., 2024; Russo et al., 2022; Silalahi et al., 2024). Further research emphasizes promptness, transparency, empathy and responsiveness-based recovery strategies in improving post-recovery satisfaction that engenders loyalty and positive behavioral intentions (Redda, 2023; Dhaniswara et al., 2023). This relationship is often even stronger in digital environments where convenience, immediate response, and personalized interactions that create greater customer attachment, and e-satisfaction becomes the key bridge linking effective service recovery to long-lasting e-loyalty in today's online marketplaces (Suthianto, 2023; Artana et al., 2021).

3. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical Framework. This research is based on Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT) by Richard L. Oliver, Equity Theory by John Stacey Adams and Commitment-Trust Theory by Robert M. Morgan and Shelby D. Hunt to understand how e-service recovery affects e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in digital consumer culture. Expectancy confirmation theory

contributes with service recovery that provides or surpasses customer's expectations, resulting in positive post-recovery evaluations and increased continued engagement; service recovery that does not produce fulfilled expectations results in increased dissatisfaction and decreased engagement (Chen & Wu, 2021; Kasunthika & Wickramarathna, 2026). According to equity theory, recovery experience judgments depend on the perceived fairness of outcomes, procedures, and interpersonal treatment. The fairness perceptions extended are a significant driver of satisfaction and engagement with an online platform (Patil et al., 2023). Indeed, trust theory emphasizes that customer confidence growing out of reliance on the platform's reputation, suitability, and responsiveness provides the root for loyalty amidst an exceptionally uncertain digital environment, where security regarding payment processing and product authenticity and the reliability of services has been ambiguous (Sciarelli et al., 2017; Söllner, 2020). Bringing these theories together, the whole provides a picture within which expectations are either reconciled or violated anchored to fairness perception under a revived consumer trust framework focused on consumer satisfaction and e-loyalty within Philippine e-retail (Raghavendra & Yashwini, 2025).

Conceptual Framework. The study's conceptual framework shows the direct and indirect links between e-service recovery, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty within the broader context of digital consumer culture on Philippines' e-retail platforms. The relationships between consumers and platforms are reflected not merely by transactional outcomes but also by post-service encounters impacting trust, satisfaction, and enduring loyalty. The framework identifies e-service recovery as a vital digital system capability which directly impacts e-loyalty through increasing trust and platform reliability and continuous user engagement that results from prompt and equitable and efficient recovery processes. E-service recovery serves as a major factor that leads to e-satisfaction because it helps customers assess their experiences after product failures when companies handle problems with efficiency, transparency, and empathy. E-satisfaction boosts e-loyalty because customers who make repeat purchases and use the platform and share positive experiences with others create a stronger bond with the platform. The model shows how e-satisfaction serves as a linking factor between e-service recovery and loyalty because e-service recovery directly affects loyalty through its ability to increase satisfaction. The research demonstrates that e-

satisfaction functions as the essential link which connects operational recovery efforts with lasting

digital customer loyalty and ongoing active participation in online marketplaces.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Showing the Relationships Among E-Service Recovery, E-Satisfaction, And E-Loyalty.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Design

This paper was analyzed through a descriptive-explanatory quantitative research design which investigated how e-service recovery and e-satisfaction and e-loyalty interconnected within Philippines digital consumer culture and its e-retail platforms. The selected approach enables researcher to describe consumer perceptions and behaviors in digitally mediated retail environments while testing causal relationships between the studied constructs. The design presents comprehensive understanding of digital recovery experiences which impact customer satisfaction and long-term loyalty while showing essential relationships that drive customer commitment and participation in modern online marketplaces.

4.2. Data Collection

The research was conducted on 405 qualified online shoppers chosen based on pre-defined inclusion criteria, such as those who had prior experience of using e-retail platforms and had encountered service-related problems to guarantee informed evaluation of e-service recovery, e-satisfaction and e-loyalty. Before data collection, G*Power analysis was conducted to determine the minimum required sample size, which was calculated at 350 respondents, based on a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$), significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), and statistical power (0.95). This justified the final sample size and proved its sufficiency for the PLS-SEM analysis, including the "10-times rule" and other

power-based recommendations (Saoula et al., 2023; Tena & Tortosa-Edo, 2023). Lastly, ethical considerations were strictly adhered to, including informed consent, voluntary participation, the right to withdraw at any time, and the protection of the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents, ensuring that all gathered data were used only for academic and research purposes.

4.3. Data Analysis

The data were analyzed by the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4, which is a variance-based structural modeling technique of preference for predictive-exploratory research as it can address the issue of several complex relationships between latent constructs present in digitally mediated environments (Mumtaz, et al., 2021; Nitzl et al., 2016). Given that PLS-SEM can examine both direct and indirect mediation effects because it is less sensitive to the assumption of multivariate normality (Hair et al., 2014), this methodology is particularly suitable for investigating how e-satisfaction mediates the relationship between e-service recovery and e-loyalty within the Philippine e-retail environment (Fong & Law, 2013; Hair et al., 2021). Advanced bootstrapping procedures within SmartPLS 4 were used to construct strong estimates of path coefficients and indirect effects on how the proposed theoretical model and mechanisms of consumer behavior in virtual commerce should be appreciated (Bido & Silva, 2019; Hair et al., 2021; Mumtaz et al., 2021). In a two-step analytical process, the measurement model permeates the first step, where it checks out

the internal consistency- Cronbach’s alpha and Composite Reliability (CR≥0.70)), internal structure (AVE≥0.50), outer loadings (≥0.70) (Table 1 & Figure 1)), discriminant validity- Fornell–Larcker criterion (Table 2), Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) (Table 3), and cross-loadings (Table 4)- all the results confirm that the constructs are reliable and empirically distinguishable amongst each other prior to going through the structural equation modeling procedure.

For structural model evaluation, bootstrapping procedures with 5,000 resamples were used to estimate and test path coefficients to generate robust estimates of standard errors, t-values, and p-values for hypothesis testing, ensuring statistically reliable assessment of the proposed direct and indirect relationships among the constructs (Bido & Silva, 2019; Hair et al., 2021; Mumtaz et al., 2021). Explanatory efficiency was also evaluated by the coefficient of determination (R²), and the models’

predictive power was measured by Q² during the method of the ranking of blindfold squared correlation coefficient, and effect sizes (f²) as an indicator of effect magnitude. To test the robustness of the model and detect potential multicollinearity problems between predictor constructs, VIFs were also used as diagnostic tools (Table 5). Further, the mediating role of e-satisfaction was assessed using the bootstrapped indirect effect analysis, a widely known, rigorous approach for mediating tests in PLS-SEM that also permits the evaluation of whether the mediating effect is partial or full (Nitzl et al., 2016). The analytical procedures were integrated to deliver a comprehensive and predictive assessment of the influence of e-service recovery on e-loyalty directly and indirectly through e-satisfaction, resulting in strong empirical evidence on digital consumer behavior and loyalty development in Philippine e-retail platforms.

Table 1: Analysis Of the Reliability and Validity of the Model Using PLS Algorithm.

Variables	Item	Loading	Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
Service Recoveries			0.862	0.882	0.899	0.642
	SER1 (INT3)	0.823				
	SER2 (INT4)	0.752				
	SER3 (TAN1)	0.779				
	SER4 (TAN2)	0.832				
Satisfaction			0.893	0.895	0.926	0.758
	SAT1 (AFF3)	0.885				
	SAT2 (AFF4)	0.86				
	SAT3 (COG1)	0.839				
	SAT4 (COG2)	0.898				
Loyalty			0.895	0.896	0.923	0.706
	L1 (RI4)	0.842				
	L2 (RI5)	0.788				
	L3 (WOM1)	0.877				
	L4 (WOM2)	0.849				
	L5 (WOM3)	0.841				

Figure 2: Factor Loading of the Construct.

Table 2: Analysis Of the Discriminant Validity Using Fornell- Larcker Criterion (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Variables	Loyalty	Satisfaction	Service Recoveries
Loyalty	0.840		
Satisfaction	0.662	0.871	
Service Recoveries	0.372	0.297	0.801

Table 3: Analysis Of the Discriminant Validity Using Heterotrait- Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Variables	Loyalty	Satisfaction	Trust
Loyalty			
Satisfaction	0.739		
Service Recoveries	0.402	0.332	

Table 4: Analysis Of the Discriminant Validity Using Cross Loadings (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Construct	Loyalty (L)	Satisfaction (SAT)	Trust(L)
SER1 (INT3)	0.269	0.263	0.823
SER2 (INT4)	0.158	0.202	0.752
SER3 (TAN1)	0.3	0.173	0.779
SER4 (TAN2)	0.404	0.259	0.832
SER5 (TI5)	0.292	0.277	0.817
SAT1 (AFF3)	0.581	0.884	0.586
SAT2 (AFF4)	0.586	0.857	0.542
SAT3 (COG1)	0.538	0.842	0.543
SAT4 (COG2)	0.597	0.899	0.585
L1 (RI4)	0.842	0.575	0.496
L2 (RI5)	0.785	0.549	0.519
L3 (WOM1)	0.877	0.588	0.512
L4 (WOM2)	0.852	0.537	0.517
L5 (WOM3)	0.844	0.526	0.503

Table 5: Multicollinearity Statistics (VIF) For Indicators Using Algorithm (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Indicators	VIF
AFF3	2.629
AFF4	2.262
COG1	2.133
COG2	2.892
INT3	2.110
INT4	2.210
RI4	2.248
RI5	1.839
TAN1	2.135
TAN2	2.260
TI5	2.483
WOM1	2.753
WOM2	2.510
WOM3	2.495
AFF3	2.629
AFF4	2.262
COG1	2.133
COG2	2.892
INT3	2.110

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Direct Effect Of E-Service Recovery On E-Loyalty

The section presents the primary results of the structural equation modelling study together with

their theoretical and practical effects which apply to the entire field of digital consumer behaviour and online shopping environments. The research findings demonstrate how e-service recovery together with e-satisfaction and e-loyalty create effects which customers use to evaluate their

relationships and their ongoing participation in digital markets. The bootstrapping results in Table 6 shows that all the direct paths in the structural model are statistically significant as the p-values are 0.000 which is less than the significance level of 0.05 and the t-values are greater than the critical value of 1.96, indicating strong empirical support for the hypothesized relationships. Besides, positive path coefficients suggest that increases in predictor variables lead to increases in outcome variables,

meaning that stronger recovery experiences and higher levels of satisfaction positively influence customer behavioural reactions. Together, these findings validate the importance of effective service recovery and positive evaluative experiences in contemporary digital marketplaces as critical drivers of consumer trust, satisfaction and long-term loyalty, and underscore the importance of responsive and consumer-centered digital service systems in maintaining long-term platform engagement.

Table 6: The Structural Model Using Botstrapping (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Variables	Path Coefficient	Standard Deviation	T-statistics	p-value
Satisfaction to Loyalty	0.608	0.048	12.575	0.000
Service Recovery to Loyalty	0.375	0.043	8.570	0.000
Service Recoveries to Satisfaction	0.302	0.051	5.878	0.000

The structural model using bootstrapping shows that the path coefficient of e-service recovery to loyalty is 0.375 with a standard deviation of 0.043, the t-statistic is 8.570, and the p-value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), which indicates a positive association between e-service recovery and e-loyalty at modest levels, but statistically significant. Specifically, for every unit improvement in e-service recovery, e-loyalty increases by 0.375 units, keeping other factors constant. High t-values above the critical value of 1.96 indicate robustness in the relationship. Overall, the p-values are highly significant, thus offering solid empirical proof for the direct effect of e-service recovery on digital retail customer loyalty. To show that effective recovery methods are not simply corrections made following a service failure but are indeed strategic catalysts of consumer trust, relational continuity, and extended digital engagement. In an era of online consumerism, an expedited response framework, transparent processes, and fair service recovery convert cases of service failure into opportunities for deepening relationships, as evident in the enhanced post-failure evaluation, consumer engagement, repeat purchases, and further loyalty toward the service (Khan et al., 2023; Cuandra et al., 2026; Pattanasing & Jiraphanumes, 2025; Hu et al., 2021; Khoa & Huynh, 2022; Alam, 2023; Tseng, 2021; Angelovska, 2023).

This study theoretically supports Expectation-Confirmation Theory, Equity Theory and Trust Theory strongly, which jointly explain how recovery events influence the behavioural outcomes after failure. If the recovery is greater than or equal to the consumer expectations, perceptions of fairness are reinforced and trust in the platform is restored. This increases the likelihood of continuous engagement and loyalty. This points to the importance of the

platform's response to service failure as being as important as the original service experience itself in the changing culture of digital consumption. This suggests that e-service recovery is an important factor in determining long-term customer-platform relationships and ongoing e-loyalty in competitive digital marketplaces.

5.2. Direct Effect Of E-Service Recovery On E-Satisfaction of Online Shoppers

The direct influence of e-service recovery on e-satisfaction in the context of digital consumer culture is crucial to understanding how digital platforms convert service disruptions into positive consumer experiences. As consumers in online retail settings become more likely to expect platforms to react to service failures with speed, fairness, transparency and empathy, recovery experiences become a key predictor of post-failure assessments. As such, the direct effect of e-service recovery on e-satisfaction indicates the instantaneous effect of recovery quality on the cognitive and emotional reassessment of consumers on their online service experience after a disruption (Ramadania, 2021). The aforementioned relation, in this digital marketing perspective, is highly defined as, with customer interaction and encounter, the service recovery will support quicker turnover, mindset of accountability, and a somewhat coherent impression that the marketplace authority has placed its emphasis on well-being.

The results demonstrate that the path coefficient from e-service-recovery to e-satisfaction is 0.302, with a t-value of 5.878 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant positive linear correlation between the two variables. The coefficient shows that when other factors are controlled, an increase of 1 unit in e-service recovery leads to an increase of 0.302 units in

e-satisfaction. This coefficient is the lowest among the direct paths studied but it is still meaningful and statistically strong. The t-value is significantly above the critical value of 1.96 and the p-value is highly significant confirming the strong empirical support for the relationship. The research suggests that when online platforms are good at handling consumer complaints with fast actions, courteous communication, and fair resolution, customer dissatisfaction will considerably decrease and favourable ratings of the platform are restored. Effective recovery is therefore a crucial strategy for regaining confidence and maintaining positive emotional and cognitive reactions to the platform in the context of digital consumer behaviour.

The findings of the study are highly consistent with Expectation-Confirmation Theory which suggests that customer satisfaction is established by comparing expectations with actual service performance. Consumers establish expectations for the platform's response to a service failure. Once the interests of the company are met or exceeded, they confirm something of value. They may respond positively towards the recovery service, and share a good perception of the service quality. Thus, implying the possible successful recovery can counteract the negative effect of service failure by turning a bad experience into the opposite, which is renewed trust and goodwill from the customer. Such a view is further supported by much empirical evidence regarding e-equality and how the setting is staged. Note in each theory which incorporates support for it-that the e-service quality and recovery function are strictly linked, and all improvements in measures of fairness, empathy, and service performance could increase e-customer satisfaction. Stehen and Barman (2023) discussed that high complaint management could drastically improve service satisfaction scores which firmly support that customers are more interested in how firms learn from their weak spots than in holding the latter against them. From the perspective of digital consumer culture, this implies that e-service recovery operates not just as an operational correction mechanism but also as a salient experience-shaping process that improves consumer satisfaction, trust and relational continuity in digital marketplaces.

5.3. Direct Effect Of E-Satisfaction On E-Loyalty

One of the key aspects of digital consumer culture is the direct relationship between e-satisfaction and e-loyalty since satisfaction drives the cognitive evaluation and emotional attachment of consumers

towards online platforms, thereby impacting long-term behavioural commitment. In digitalized marketplaces, where consumers have instant access to competing options, loyalty increasingly depends on the platform's ability to continually deliver experiences that match or exceed customer expectations. Previous literature consistently suggests that higher levels of customer satisfaction greatly drive retention, repeat purchases, and continued use of the website or online marketplace (Ahmed et al., 2021; AL-Ghaswyneh et al., 2025; Tirtayasa et al., 2024). It is important to mention that an identical relationship can be seen operating in the context of e-commerce. Empirical data suggests that e-satisfaction exerts primarily a strong, long-lasting positive effect on e-loyalty, confirming that a strong digital experience is at the heart of building lasting relationships between a consumer and the platform. (Lesmana & Balqiah, 2023; Mittal & Kaur, 2023).

The path indicator for e-satisfaction to e-loyalty is equal to 0.608, with the respective t-value exceeding 12.575 ($p = .000$). This is such a strong and extremely significant relationship that a single contribution to one of these constructs calls for the simultaneous contribution from the other part as well. So, whenever e-loyalty improves one more unit of movement upwards, there definitely will be an increase in unit movement upwards with e-satisfaction in line with the other antecedents. Within the structural model these are the coefficients indicated as the direct paths to have the path coefficient the highest is the-line pointing to e-loyalty very much more than the coefficient the path for e-satisfaction, suggesting that this latter is the first antecedent of e-loyalty.

The high t-value demonstrates that these two strength levels and persistence level exist. The research results show strong statistical evidence for the proposed relationship because they achieved results which reached $p < 0.000$. The research results show that e-retail satisfaction directly influences customers to make repeat purchases and maintain their connection with the platform while recommending it to others. The research shows that customer satisfaction functions as a critical factor which enables businesses to maintain their digital customer connections beyond the initial period.

The result provides theoretical evidence which supports Expectation-Confirmation Theory because the theory states that customer satisfaction develops into ongoing usage and loyalty when their actual experiences match or exceed their initial expectations. Digital retail environment uses customer contentment to measure successful

transactions which lead to consumers experiencing platform convenience and trustworthiness and responsiveness and relational value. This supports the reasoning that the e-satisfaction is not an outcome variable but a fundamental cultural and behavioural factor that affects consumer attachment in digital markets. Such a discovery is further reinforced by previous research findings in which e-satisfaction constitutes a considerable increase in e-loyalty and further enhances online consumer commitment (Sihombing et al., 2023; Sudirjo et al., 2024). Also, research supports the view of satisfaction as being a crucial mediator between service quality dimensions and loyalty outcomes, thus, underlining its role in mutual development for loyal customer relationships (Cotarelo et al., 2021). Similar are the findings presented by Al-Dwairi et al. (2024) and Dwivedi (2023), explaining that satisfaction has a direct and significantly positive impact on consumer loyalty, thus making it one of the critical ingredients for holding on to the e-commerce client. In the ongoing quest for fulfilment and significant interactions related to the database, websites that recognize the immense value of customers tend to cultivate loyalty, turn customers into strong advocates, and build lasting commitment in the evolving digital marketplace (Louisa & Simbolon, 2023).

5.4. Mediating Role Of E-Satisfaction in the Effects Of E-Service Recovery On E-Loyalty

The mediating role of e-satisfaction sheds more light on the impact of e-service recovery on e-loyalty in the broader context of digital consumer culture, indicating that customer loyalty in digital marketplaces is determined not only by the immediate recovery actions but also by the satisfaction consumers get from those recovery experiences. Using an indirect approach, this study identifies the psychological and relational reasons via which the effective service recovery leads to long-term client commitment. In digitally mediated contexts, consumers' assessment of a problem resolution includes not just the question of whether the problem has been handled, but also how the recovery experience shapes their opinions of value, fairness, and platform responsiveness. Thus, the mediation of e-satisfaction must be investigated in terms of how digital platforms may convert service failures into opportunities for stronger customer attachment, and thus for a firmer and long-lasting customer support (Antwi et al., 2022). In this line of thought, previous studies have established that customer satisfaction is a significant mediating factor between service quality and loyalty (Hess, 2020) and

that service failures, well managed, contribute indirectly to loyalty by way of enhancing satisfaction after recovery (Muharam, Wakhidjaka, & Heru, 2021; Purnamasari & Suryandari, 2023; Redda, 2023).

The findings of mediation study (Table 7) shows that the e-service recovery has a significant indirect effect on e-loyalty through e-satisfaction ($\beta = 0.180$, $t = 4.856$, $p = 0.000$). It also shows the positive and significant mediating link. This means that the coefficient implies that an increase of 1 unit of e-service recovery will enhance e-loyalty by 0.180 units indirectly through e-satisfaction, *ceteris paribus*. The high t-value, which is far greater than the crucial value of 1.96, confirms the significance of the indirect pathway, and the highly significant p-value gives strong empirical support for the mediating role of e-satisfaction. This research implies that good recovery tactics promote loyalty not only through direct recovery efforts but also by enhancing consumers' satisfaction with the platform after a service outage. This shows that satisfaction works as a crucial relational bridge inside digital consumer environment, transforming operational recovery efforts into greater emotional reassurance, restored trust, and enduring behavioural commitment.

From a theoretical point of view, this study gives strong support to Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT) that states that satisfaction occurs when real service experiences are equal to or better than client expectations. When service recovery is involved, customers also form expectations regarding the appropriate responses of the online platforms to service failures. If the recovery efforts are perceived as timely, fair and effective, positive confirmation will occur, leading to greater post-recovery satisfaction and eventually enhanced loyalty. The mediating pathway indicates that the building of loyalty in digital markets is not only a consequence of service recovery but also strongly influenced by how recovery experiences influence consumers' evaluative and emotional responses. Thus, empirical evidence further establishes that the mediating role of e-satisfaction should crucially connect e-service quality, e-trust, and e-loyalty, thereby changing positive experiences with digital services with long-term customer loyalty (Florence & Aprillia, 2025). Similar studies have shown that the mediating impact of e-satisfaction from perceived value to e-loyalty changes short-term consumer perceptions into long-term relational commitments (Kalim et al., 2024; Setiyono et al., 2023). The study emphasizes that companies should build satisfaction with recovery events designed to reconstruct belief, boost satisfaction, and anchor consumers' long-term

attachment to the platform while also linking these experiences with continued e-loyalty (Chmeis &

Zaiter, 2024).

Table 7: Analysis Of the Mediation Model Using Bootstrapping (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Variables	Path	Path Coefficient	Standard Deviation	T-statistics	p-value
Service Recoveries->Satisfaction-> Loyalty	Indirect Effects	0.180	0.037	0.4856	0.000

5.5. Analysis Of F², R², And Q² Using PLS Algorithm and Blindfolding

The results from the PLS algorithm and blindfolding procedures have substantial implications on the magnitude of the effect size (f²), the explanatory power (R²) and the predictive relevance (Q²) (Table 8) of the structural model of e-service recovery, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty in the context of Philippine digital consumer culture. The effect size analysis shows a strong effect for the path e-satisfaction to e-loyalty (f² = 0.633) that surpasses the threshold for large effect by far and suggests e-satisfaction as the most influential driver of e-loyalty with a central role in shaping sustained digital consumer commitment. On the other hand, the paths e-service recovery to e-loyalty (f² = 0.063) and e-service recovery to e-satisfaction (f² = 0.097) have weak effect sizes suggesting that although recovery mechanisms have lower direct contributions, they are still important as experience-shaping catalysts,

restoring confidence, rebuilding trust and creating the conditions required for satisfaction to grow and, ultimately, foster loyalty.

Furthermore, a low Q² effect value is further testimony to the fact that only e-service recovery is relevant to e-satisfaction (0.088), through which trust, service quality, platform usability, convenience, personalization, and perceived value play a significant role. This is in congruence with the predictive validity (Q²) determination, evidenced by a high Q² value for e-loyalty (0.326) and the Q² for e-satisfaction (0.066). Thus, it can be concluded that the model reveals properties that establish the potential for predicting loyalty outcomes in the future. Taken together, these results suggest that satisfaction-based relational mechanisms are the main drivers of e-loyalty in digital consumer culture, whereas e-satisfaction is driven by a wider and more complex set of digital experiences, thus highlighting the multidimensional nature of consumer engagement in e-retail platforms.

Table 8: Analysis Of F² And R² Using PLS Algorithm, And Q² (Service Recoveries- Satisfaction- Loyalty).

Variables	f ²	Effect Size	R ²	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Satisfaction->Loyalty	0.633	Strong		
Service Recoveries -> Loyalty	0.063	Weak		
Service Recoveries-> Satisfaction	0.097	Weak		
Loyalty			0.472	0.326
Satisfaction			0.088	0.066

6. CONCLUSION

This study examines the links between e-service recovery, e-satisfaction and e-loyalty in the context of the Philippine digital consumer culture, and investigates both direct and mediating pathways through which post-service recovery experiences impact long-term consumer commitment in e-retail platforms. The results provide empirical evidence that digital consumer loyalty is not only constructed on transactional efficiency, but on the quality of post-failure interactions, evaluative satisfaction and the platform’s ability to maintain meaningful consumer relationships in digitally mediated environments.

a. The e-service recovery has a direct effect on e-loyalty, which shows its importance as a digital system ability in maintaining customer retention and enhancing consumer-platform interactions. In

practical terms, this means that e-retail platforms need to invest in effective, quick, transparent and customer-centric recovery procedures to retain trust and encourage continuing involvement after service disruptions. This theoretically supports the notion that service encounters after failure are not only corrective operational roles, but rather strategic relationship-building tools that impact consumer commitment in digital marketplaces.

b. The style of platform response on service failures has a big impact on the consumer evaluation of the online experience, which means e-service recovery has a strong influence on e-satisfaction. This means that justice, empathy and prompt resolution of issues must be at the core of organizations’ digital service management. This study has theoretical implications in that it supports perspectives that emphasize expectation fulfillment, perceived justice,

and emotional comfort as important drivers of pleasure in online service encounters, strengthening the relational and experiential features of digital consumer culture.

c. E-satisfaction was found to be the biggest predictor of e-loyalty proving that consumer contentment is the most powerful mechanism generating long-term digital engagement, repeat patronage and positive advocacy. This means that e-retail platforms have to give topmost priority to customer satisfaction in all their strategic cycles, continually polishing service quality, user experience, convenience, post-transaction support. The research backs the theoretical framework of consumer behavior models suggesting satisfaction as the primary antecedent of loyalty, especially in digital environments where emotional and experiential assessments affect behavioral intentions.

d. E-satisfaction plays an important mediating role between e-service recovery and e-loyalty, indicating that the efficiency of recovery tactics in developing loyalty is primarily dependent on their ability to generate real customer satisfaction. Therefore, firms must do more than just fix service failures and develop recovery experiences that rebuild confidence, maintain trust, and produce positive emotional outcomes for consumers. This mediation effect theoretically contributes to a more sophisticated view of post-service failure dynamics, indicating e-satisfaction as the crucial relational bridge that transforms recovery experiences into long-lasting loyalty in today's digital consumer culture.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the substantial linkages between e-service recovery, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty, the following recommendations are offered to enhance the digital consumer experience, establish platform-customer interactions, and develop long-term loyalty in the Philippine e-retail ecosystems:

a. Make e-satisfaction a key strategic driver of connection with digital consumers. E-satisfaction was the strongest predictor of e-loyalty. As such, e-retail platforms should pay more attention to the provision of seamless, trustworthy and satisfying digital experiences, such as efficient transactions, correct product information, user-friendly interfaces, and reliable delivery systems. Consistently pleasant experiences create emotional attachment, promote repeat consumption, and build long-term customer-platform relationships within the broader digital consumer culture.

b. Enhance e-service recovery as a relationship

building tool rather than a corrective measure. Given that e-service recovery has a substantial impact on e-satisfaction and e-loyalty, firms should improve their recovery systems through quick response times, clear communication, just resolutions and compassionate customer interaction. Recovery activities must be planned not simply to repair service problems, but also to restore consumer confidence and provide positive post-failure experiences that promote trust and platform credibility.

c. Design customer-first recovery solutions to increase satisfaction after recovery. Because e-satisfaction mediates the relationship between e-service recovery and e-loyalty, e-retailers should make sure that recovery efforts lead to meaningful consumer satisfaction, rather than simply fixing operational difficulties. Personalized replies, emotionally intelligent communication, proactive follow-up, and compensating strategies that match customer expectations can turn service failures into opportunities to build better consumer loyalty and stronger relational relationships.

d. Embed recovery and satisfaction processes into the planning of digital platforms. E-retail platforms should include technology-based recovery solutions into their digital ecosystem such as automatic complaint tracking, AI-assisted customer assistance, real-time response channels, transparent refund systems and feedback monitoring tools. Embedding recovery in the system architecture helps the platform to be more responsive and helps in building a more flexible, customer-centric and culture responsive digital retail environment.

e. Explore more about the wider facets of digital consumer experience. With limited explanatory power for e-satisfaction, future research should investigate other drivers, including trust, perceived value, service quality, platform usability, personalization, and digital convenience for better understanding of loyalty formation in the online retail environment. By venturing into these wider sensory and relational domains, we will achieve a more thorough grasp of the transformation of digital consumer culture and the building of enduring loyalty in markets increasingly reliant on technology.

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Several methodological constraints of this study may impact the interpretation and generalizability of its conclusions concerning digital consumer culture. First, the cross-sectional research design only captures consumer perceptions and behavioral evaluations at one point in time. It is limited in fully establishing causal relationships among e-service

recovery, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty, especially when digital consumer attitudes and platform experiences are continuously evolving in response to technological and market changes. Second, the study relied on self-reported measurements, which could be affected by response biases such as social desirability, recollection bias, or subjective interpretation of digital service experiences. Although the sample size was statistically adequate and empirically justified, the non-probability sampling method and the focus on a specific segment of online buyers may limit the generalizability of the findings to the wider and more diversified population of digital customers. Thus, the present study provides relevant insights on consumer behavior in Philippine e-retail platforms, while the findings should be understood within the contextual constraints of the sample, research design and the dynamic nature of digital consumption.

9. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Future research should go beyond cross-sectional approaches and utilize longitudinal and experimental research designs to better capture the evolving nature of digital consumer culture and to establish stronger causal explanations for the relationships among e-service recovery, e-satisfaction, and e-loyalty. The authors suggest that, in addition to the study's implications, the conceptual model should be enhanced by including

constructs such as trust, perceived value, e-service quality, platform usability, personalization, and user experience, and by examining moderating variables such as age, digital literacy, platform type, and shopping frequency to achieve a deeper and more detailed understanding of consumer behaviour in digitally mediated markets. Such enhancements would improve the explanatory power of the model and provide more profound insights into the relational and experiential factors that underpin long-term digital consumer engagement.

Furthermore, future research should examine the effects of the use of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, chatbots, predictive analytics, and automated recovery systems on service recovery experiences and customer satisfaction and loyalty in technology-driven retail ecosystems. Cross-cultural and multi-context studies are also encouraged to study the impact of cultural values, social conventions, and varied digital infrastructures on post-recovery consumer behaviour across various markets. Furthermore, qualitative and mixed-method approaches could offer a more distinct insight into how consumers emotionally and intellectually make sense of digital healing experiences. Collectively, these future directions will contribute to building more flexible, culturally relevant and consumer-oriented digital commerce systems, as well as to enhancing the overall academic understanding of loyalty formation in the expanding world of digital consumer culture.

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REFERENCES

- Aguilar-Rojas, Ó., Herrera, C. F., & Pérez-Rueda, A. (2024). The importance of social comparison in perceived justice during the service recovery process. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 33(4), 488–504. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ejmbe-02-2023-0056>
- Ahmed, R. R., Štreimikienė, D., Channar, Z. A., Soomro, R. H., & Štreimikis, J. (2021). E-banking Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: Evidence from Serial Mediation through Modified E-S-QUAL Model and Second-Order PLS-SEM. *Engineering Economics*, 32(5), 407–421. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.32.5.28997>
- Akarsu, T. N., Marvi, R., & Foroudi, P. (2022). Service failure research in the hospitality and tourism industry: a synopsis of past, present and future dynamics from 2001 to 2020. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 35(1), 186–217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijchm-11-2021-1441>
- Alam, M. Z. (2023). An investigation on the use of digital marketing towards the customer satisfaction and brand loyalty of hotels/ restaurants sector in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(4), 1493–1504. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2023.8.013>

- Al-Dwairi, R. M., Shehabat, I., Zahrawi, A., & Hammouri, Q. (2024). Building customer trust, loyalty, and satisfaction: The power of social media in e-commerce environments. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 8(3), 1883–1894. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2024.2.001>
- AL-Ghaswyneh, O. F. M., Al-Refai, A. N., Abubaker, M. M., Al-Ajlouni, M. M., & Saad, M. (2025). Using Digital Marketing Engineering Towards E-Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Jordanian Malls among Millennials. *Engineering Technology & Applied Science Research*, 15(5), 26792–26799. <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.12375>
- Alhawbani, G. S., Ali, N., & Hammouda, A.-N. M. (2021). The Effect of Service Recovery Strategies on Satisfaction with the Recovery: The Mediating Role of Distributive Justice. *European Journal of Business Management and Research*, 6(3), 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2021.6.3.819>
- Al-Mu'ani, L., Al-Momani, M. M., Amayreh, A., Aladwan, S. I., & Al-Rahmi, W. M. (2024). The effect of logistics and policy service quality on customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty in quick commerce: A multigroup analysis of generation Y and generation Z. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 12(3), 1417–1432. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2024.4.009>
- Angelovska, N. (2023). Studying Customer E-loyalty to Online Intermediary: Case of Group Buying Site. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce Studies*, 14(2), 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.7903/ijecs.2120>
- Antwi, S., Gbolonyo, P. K., & Jiang, C. (2022). Do E-Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction Affect Loyalty in E-Retailing? Evidence from Ghanaian Online Consumers. *TIJAB (The International Journal of Applied Business)*, 6(1), 17–34. <https://doi.org/10.20473/tijab.v6.i1.2022.32706>
- Anwar, S., & Ozuem, W. (2022). An integrated service recovery process for service failures: insights from systematic review. *Qualitative Market Research An International Journal*, 25(4), 433–452. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qmr-12-2021-0147>
- Anwar, S., Mochlasin, M., Puspita, R. E., Annisa, A. A., Rofiuddin, M., & Nabila, R. (2021). Loyalty and Word of Mouth of Muslim Women who Use Mobile Commerce in Indonesia. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 317, 5018–5018. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202131705018>
- Arifin, Moh. S., Maulana, M. F., Suroso, A., Suhartono, S., & Mariam, M. (2023). The Role of E-Customer Satisfaction as Intervening Variable in Relationship Between E-Service Quality, E-Recovery and E-Customer Loyalty of Indonesian Railroad Access Customers. *Jurnal Sistim Informasi Dan Teknologi*, 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.60083/jsisfotek.v5i3.274>
- Artana, I. M., Fattah, H., Putra, I. G. J. E., Sariyani, N. L. P., Nadir, M., Asnawati, A., & Rismawati, R. (2021). Repurchase intention behavior in B2C E-commerce. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 6(1), 147–154. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2021.9.013>
- Ashiq, R., & Hussain, A. (2023). Exploring the effects of e-service quality and e-trust on consumers' e-satisfaction and e-loyalty: insights from online shoppers in Pakistan. *Journal of Electronic Business & Digital Economics*, 3(2), 117–141. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jebde-09-2023-0019>
- Bido, D. de S., & Silva, D. da. (2019). SmartPLS 3: especificação, estimação, avaliação e relato. *Administração Ensino e Pesquisa*, 20(2), 488–536. <https://doi.org/10.13058/raep.2019.v20n2.1545>
- Chen, Y., & Wu, I.-J. (2021). Understanding the role of webcare in the online buying service recovery context. *Enterprise Information Systems*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17517575.2021.1943761>
- Chmeis, S. T. J. E., & Zaiter, R. (2024). THE IMPACT OF E-SERVICE QUALITY ON E-LOYALTY THROUGH THE MEDIATING EFFECTS OF E-SATISFACTION AND E-TRUST IN LEBANON. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v12i2.2770>
- Chokpiriyawat, T., & Siriyota, K. (2024). The Impact of Service Recovery Actions and Perceived Justice on Customer Satisfaction: Insights from Thailand's Private Hospitals. *International Journal of Analysis and Applications*, 22, 81–81. <https://doi.org/10.28924/2291-8639-22-2024-81>
- Costa, P., & Rodrigues, H. (2023). The ever-changing business of e-commerce-net benefits while designing a new platform for small companies. *Review of Managerial Science*, 18(9), 2507–2545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00681-6>
- Cotarelo, M., García, H. C., & Gardó, T. F. (2021). A further approach in omnichannel LSQ, satisfaction and customer loyalty. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 49(8), 1133–1153. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijrdm-01-2020-0013>
- Cuandra, F., Christina, C., Purwianti, L., Yulianto, E., & Susanto, S. (2026). PENGARUH E-SERVICE QUALITY DAN E-SERVICE RECOVERY TERHADAP LOYALITAS PELANGGAN E-COMMERCE MELALUI KEPERCAYAAN DAN KEPUASAN. *Equilibrium Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Manajemen Dan Akuntansi*, 15(1),

- 69–69. <https://doi.org/10.35906/equili.v15i1.2750>
- Dehkordi, M. A., & Nasr, A. K. (2025). How perceptions of service failure stability, service recovery justice and e-service quality affect value co-creation intentions in two-sided e-retail platforms. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 17(3), 355–380. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijqss-12-2024-0196>
- Dhaigude, A. S., Tapar, A. V., Jawed, M. S., & Kamath, G. B. (2023). Is perceived value enough to create loyalty for m-wallets? Exploring the role of trust and satisfaction. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2281050>
- Dhaniswara, E., Wahyuningsih, S. S., Eldo, H., Bakri, A. A., & Junaidi, A. (2023). The Influence of Electronic Service Quality and Electronic Recovery on Online Re-Purchase Intention: Role of E-Loyalty as Intervening Variable. *Jurnal Sistim Informasi Dan Teknologi*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.60083/jsisfotek.v5i3.271>
- Dwivedi, S. (2023). Identification of facing satisfaction issue while shopping through electronic platforms in gen- X and Y. *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 18(3), 78–89. <https://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-27242023000300078>
- E-commerce Evolution in Asia and the Pacific*. (2023). <https://doi.org/10.22617/tcs230473-2>
- Fang, zhengyang, Juanatas, R., Niguidula, J., & Zhou, W. (2022). Optimization of China ASEAN Cross-Border E-Commerce Development Path Under the Background of RCEP in the Post Epidemic Era. In *Advances in economics, business and management research/Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research* (pp. 1864–1868). Atlantis Press. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-036-7_278
- Florence, J., & Aprillia, A. (2025). E-Satisfaction as a Mediator Between E-Service Quality, E-Trust, and E-Loyalty. *Aptisi Transactions on Management (ATM)*, 9(2), 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.33050/atm.v9i2.2434>
- Fong, L. H. N., & Law, R. (2013). Hair, J. F. Jr., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M. (2014). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Sage Publications. ISBN: 978-1-4522-1744-4. 307 pp. *European Journal of Tourism Research*, 6(2), 211–213. <https://doi.org/10.54055/ejtr.v6i2.134>
- Foroudi, P., Tabaghdehi, S. A. H., Cillo, V., & Cuomo, M. T. (2024). E-service failure and recovery strategy in times of crisis: effect on peer attitudes, expectation and future intention. *Review of Managerial Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-024-00762-0>
- Gani, L., Fonda, L., Prasetyo, S. H., & Gunadi, W. (2024). The Effect of Service Recovery on Customer Satisfaction, eWOM, and Repurchase Intention in the Online Travel Agent (OTA) Industry in Indonesia with Service Failure Severity as Moderator. *Jurnal Manajemen Teknologi*, 23(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.12695/jmt.2024.23.1.1>
- Gelbrich, K., & Roschk, H. (2010). A Meta-Analysis of Organizational Complaint Handling and Customer Responses. *Journal of Service Research*, 14(1), 24–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670510387914>
- GÜLER, E. S. (2023). THE FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN E-COMMERCE: THE EXAMP. *Route Educational and Social Science Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.17121/ressjournal.3481>
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R. In *Classroom companion: business*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7>
- Han, S., Anderson, C., & Chung, K. (2023). Do managerial communications improve customer satisfaction and eWOM? The moderating effect of response authenticity. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01979-2>
- Hu, N., Chen, X., & Zhang, N. (2021). Influence of Service Quality of Agricultural Products E-Commerce Platform on Customer Loyalty - The Mediating Role of Customer Engagement. *International Journal of Smart Business and Technology*, 9(1), 13–28. <https://doi.org/10.21742/ijstb.2021.9.1.02>
- Indrawati, E. P., Yulianto, E., & Abdillah, Y. (2024). Analysis of the Effect of E-Recovery Service Quality and E-Service Quality on E-Customer Satisfaction and E-Customer Royalty. *KnE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i11.15837>
- Jeddy, S. (2024). ANALYZING THE ANTECEDENTS OF E-REPURCHASING: A MODEL FRAMEWORK WITH MEDIATING ROLE OF SATISFACTION. *Management Theory and Studies for Rural Business and Infrastructure Development*, 46(2), 213–219. <https://doi.org/10.15544/mts.2024.22>
- Kalim, M. N., Prasetyo, W. B., Ramli, A. H., & Mariam, S. (2024). Perceived Value, E-Trust, E-Satisfaction, and

- E-Loyalty on Online Trip Clients in Jakarta. *Majalah Ilmiah Bijak*, 21(1), 86–102. <https://doi.org/10.31334/bijak.v21i1.3673>
- Kasunthika, R. K., & Wickramarathna, K. G. M. H. (2026). E-Service Quality of E-Tailors on E-Repurchase Intention: A Comprehensive Literature Review. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(3), 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2026.143006>
- Khan, F. N., Arshad, M. U., & Munir, M. M. (2023). Impact of e-service quality on e-loyalty of online banking customers in Pakistan during the Covid-19 pandemic: mediating role of e-satisfaction. *Future Business Journal*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00201-8>
- Khoa, B. T., & Huỳnh, T. T. (2022). The influence of social media marketing activities on customer loyalty: A study of e-commerce industry. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(1), 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2022.11.005>
- Kim, K., & Ha, H. (2023). The dynamics of perceived justice and its outcomes in the online tourism sector: inter-relationships and temporal and carryover effects. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 27(24), 4740–4756. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2023.2280145>
- Kim, S., & Kandampully, J. (2011). Exploring Customer Loyalty Following Service Recovery: The Relationships of Perceived Justice, Commitment, Trust, and Loyalty. *ScholarWorks@UMassAmherst (University of Massachusetts Amherst)*. https://scholarworks.umass.edu/gradconf_hospitality/2011/Poster/93
- Komunda, M. B., & Osarenkhoe, A. (2023). Can Efficacious Service Recovery Enable Retention of Complaint-Averse Savvy Customers? *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 16(6), 670–693. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jssm.2023.166036>
- Kurniadi, H., & Rana, J. A. S. (2023). The power of trust: How does consumer trust impact satisfaction and loyalty in Indonesian digital business? *Innovative Marketing*, 19(2), 236–249. [https://doi.org/10.21511/im.19\(2\).2023.19](https://doi.org/10.21511/im.19(2).2023.19)
- Lesmana, A., & Balqiah, T. E. (2023). Enhancing Customer E-Loyalty and E-WOM: The Role of Electronic and Non-Electronic Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction (PLN Mobile Application). *Petra International Journal of Business Studies*, 6(2), 201–212. <https://doi.org/10.9744/petraijbs.6.2.201-212>
- Liao, Y. K., Wu, C. Y., Truong, G. N. T., & Thi, Y. (2022). The Roles of Service Recovery and Perceived Justice on Post-Recovery Satisfaction in M-Commerce. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 14838–14838. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142214838>
- Lim, W. M., Saha, V., & Das, M. (2025). From service failure to brand loyalty: evidence of service recovery paradox. *Journal of Brand Management*, 32(4), 257–281. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41262-025-00380-5>
- Louisa, L., & Simbolon, F. P. (2023). Determinants of Customer Loyalty: Empirical Study from Online Food Delivery Services. *Binus Business Review*, 14(3), 247–258. <https://doi.org/10.21512/bbr.v14i3.9233>
- Lova, A. N., & Budaya, I. (2023). Behavioral of Customer Loyalty on E-Commerce: The Mediating Effect of E-Satisfaction in Tiktok Shop. *Journal of Scientific Research Education and Technology (JSRET)*, 2(1), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.58526/jsret.v2i1.43>
- Lu, C., & Segumpan, R. G. (2025). The Impact of Service Recovery Quality on Customer Behavioral Intentions in TikTok E-Mall: The Mediating Role of Perceived Justice. *Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Studies*, 1(1), 38–44. <https://doi.org/10.26855/jpbs.2025.06.007>
- Mendoza, E. C. (2021). A STUDY OF ONLINE CUSTOMERS REPURCHASE INTENTION USING THE 4RS OF MARKETING FRAMEWORK. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 11(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.32479/irmm.11009>
- Mir, M., Ashraf, R., Syed, T. A., Ali, S., & Nawaz, R. (2023). Mapping the service recovery research landscape: A bibliometric-based systematic review. *Psychology and Marketing*, 40(10), 2060–2087. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21864>
- Mittal, E., & Kaur, N. (2023). Building e-Loyalty towards Online Food Delivery Apps: A Serial-Mediation Model. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.21315/aamj2023.28.1.6>
- Montaño, V. E., & Mercado, J. L. L. (2023). DYNAMIC RELATIONSHIPS: E-COMMERCE SALES AND KEY EXOGENOUS VARIABLES IN THE PHILIPPINES. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejmms.v8i3.1603>
- Muharam, H., Chaniago, H., Endraria, E., & Harun, A. (2021). E-Service Quality, Customer Trust and Satisfaction: Market Place Consumer Loyalty Analysis. *JURNAL MINDS Manajemen Ide Dan Inspirasi*, 8(2), 237–237. <https://doi.org/10.24252/minds.v8i2.23224>
- Mumtaz, A. H., Ramayah, T., Cheah, J., Ting, H., Chuah, F., Cham, T., Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Becker, J.-M.

- (2021). *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, 5(1). [https://doi.org/10.47263/jasem.5\(1\)](https://doi.org/10.47263/jasem.5(1))
- Nitzl, C., Roldán, J. L., & Cepeda-Carrión, G. (2016). Mediation analysis in partial least squares path modeling. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 116(9), 1849–1864. <https://doi.org/10.1108/imds-07-2015-0302>
- Ozuem, W., Willis, M., Ranfagni, S., Howell, K. E., & Rovai, S. (2023). Dynamics of user-generated content and service failure recovery: evidence from millennials. *Qualitative Market Research An International Journal*, 26(5), 600–631. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qmr-08-2022-0124>
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Malhotra, A. (2005). E-S-QUAL: A multiple-item scale for assessing electronic service quality. *Carolina Digital Repository (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)*. <https://doi.org/10.17615/1mdx-dp60>
- Patil, D., Rane, N. L., & Patil, D. Y. (2023). Customer experience and satisfaction: Importance of customer reviews and customer value on buying preference. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*. <https://doi.org/10.56726/irjmets36460>
- Pattanasang, K., & Jiraphanumes, K. (2025). Influence of Electronic Service Quality on Relationship Quality, Customer Engagement and Loyalty: Evidence of Ornamental Plants Online Businesses in Thailand. *TEM Journal*, 2812–2823. <https://doi.org/10.18421/tem143-81>
- Phan, A. C., Nguyen, H. T., & Pham, T. X. T. (2020). Relationship between service recovery, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Empirical evidence from e-retailing. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2020.12.007>
- Purnamasari, I., & Suryandari, R. T. (2023). Effect of E-Service Quality on E-Repurchase Intention in Indonesia Online Shopping: E-Satisfaction and E-Trust as Mediation Variables. *European Journal of Business Management and Research*, 8(1), 155–161. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2023.8.1.1766>
- Qiang, H. Z. (2023). The Relationship between Service Remediation, Perceived Fairness, Customer Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention: A Case Study of Online Stores in the Yangtze River Delta Region of China. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 27(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.58970/ijsb.2161>
- Raghavendra, D., & Yashwini. (2025). Future Research Directions for Expectation Confirmation Theory in Cross-Cultural and Emerging Digital Environments. *Asian Review of Social Sciences*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.70112/arss-2025.14.1.4288>
- Ramadania, R. (2021). E-S-Qual and E-Recs-Qual Toward Customer Satisfaction, Trust and Loyalty in Electronic Banking Services During The Covid-19 Pandemic. *Matrik Jurnal Manajemen Strategi Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan*, 100–100. <https://doi.org/10.24843/matrik:jmbk.2021.v15.i01.p09>
- Redda, E. H. (2023). E-banking quality and customer loyalty: The mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 18(2), 177–188. [https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.18\(2\).2023.15](https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.18(2).2023.15)
- Rohmayati, N. S., & Hidayat, R. (2022). Impact of Service Quality and Complaint Management on Customer Satisfaction Case Study from E-Commerce Marketing Client Lazada. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 149, 3012–3012. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202214903012>
- Rosli, N. N. (2025). FROM SERVICE FAILURES TO CUSTOMER LOYALTY: A HOLISTIC REVIEW OF SERVICE RECOVERY PERFORMANCE. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management Practices*, 8(29), 163–175. <https://doi.org/10.35631/ijemp.829012>
- Russo, I., Masorgo, N., & Gligor, D. (2022). Examining the impact of service recovery resilience in the context of product replacement: the roles of perceived procedural and interactional justice. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 52(8), 638–672. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijpdlm-07-2021-0301>
- Sadiq, M. W., Huo, C., Almogren, A. S., Aljammaz, N. A., Al-Rahmi, W. M., Al-Maatouk, Q., & Zulfiqar, S. (2022). Innovation in Neighborhood Management Web Service: A Precise Initiative to Augment Audiences' Interaction on Social Media. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.920112>
- Saoula, O., Shamim, A., Suki, N. M., Ahmad, M. J., Abid, M. F., Patwary, A. K., & Abbasi, A. Z. (2023). Building e-trust and e-retention in online shopping: the role of website design, reliability and perceived ease of use. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 27(2), 178–201. <https://doi.org/10.1108/sjme-07-2022-0159>
- Sarboini, S., Syahputra, H., Adam, M., Foster, B., Pasaribu, M. R., & Saputra, J. (2025). Investigating the effect of e-service quality on customer loyalty within the online marketplace during the covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 9(3), 613–622. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2024.8.006>
- Sarilgan, A. E., & Yücel, M. F. (2024). The Mediation Role of Passenger Overall Satisfaction in the Effect of

- Complaint Satisfaction on Repurchase Intention: An Empirical Study on Airline Passengers. *DergiPark (Istanbul University)*. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/gumus/issue/90217/1560434>
- Sciarelli, M., Nagm, A. A., Dakrory, M. I., Tani, M., & Khashan, M. A. (2017). The Relationship between Service Recovery and Patronage Intentions: The Mediating Role of Relationship Quality. *International Business Research*, 10(8), 215–215. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v10n8p215>
- Setiyono, A., Chandrawatisma, C., Fanandi, R. H. S., & Heriyati, P. (2023). Antecedents of E-Loyalty as Research for the Quick Commerce Industry. *Interdisciplinary Social Studies*, 2(8), 2287–2299. <https://doi.org/10.55324/iss.v2i8.456>
- Sihombing, N. S., Simbolon, S., Susanto, A., & Tarigan, S. A. (2023). E-Service Quality And E-Trust Toward Online Shop Customers E-Loyalty: Satisfaction as Mediation. *Amwaluna Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 7(2), 274–289. <https://doi.org/10.29313/amwaluna.v7i2.11458>
- Silalahi, R. A., Wijaya, C., Iswari, F. P., & Simanjuntak, E. R. (2024). The Role of Perceived Justice within the Service Recovery Context in the Online Marketplace Moderated by Failure Severity. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences (PJLSS)*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.57239/pjls-2024-22.1.00489>
- Sohaib, M., Safeer, A. A., & Majeed, A. (2022). Role of social media marketing activities in China's e-commerce industry: A stimulus organism response theory context. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.941058>
- Söllner, M. (2020, January 1). Same Same but Different? A Two-Foci Perspective on Trust in Information Systems. *Proceedings of the ... Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences/Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.24251/hicss.2020.630>
- Sousa, R., & Voss, C. (2009). The effects of service failures and recovery on customer loyalty in e-services. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 29(8), 834–864. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443570910977715>
- Sudirjo, F., Sari, E. N., Yuliani, Y., Hendra, H., & Apramilda, R. (2024). The Role of Customer Trust Toward Digital Sales and Website Visitor Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty of Zara Indonesia. *Jurnal Informasi Dan Teknologi*, 291–296. <https://doi.org/10.60083/jidt.v6i1.517>
- Suthianto, C. F. Y. (2023). The Impact of Brand Equity, E-Brand Experience, and Web Entertainment Toward E-Satisfaction and E-Loyalty on Marketplace. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce Studies*, 14(1), 95–95. <https://doi.org/10.7903/ijecs.2158>
- Syafriani, M., & Hidayah, D. N. (2025). The Influence Of E-Service Quality And E-Recovery On E-Satisfaction and Its Implications For E-Loyalty of Shopee User in Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 22(2), 122–135. <https://doi.org/10.31849/2xt35n60>
- Tahir, Z. (2021). Effectiveness of offline and online rewards in restoring satisfaction and trust. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 25(3), 409–424. <https://doi.org/10.1108/sjme-07-2021-0143>
- Tena, M. Á. M., & Tortosa-Edo, V. (2023). Multirooming: generating e-satisfaction throughout omnichannel consumer journey design and online customer experience. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 18(3), 349–369. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrim-05-2023-0149>
- Tengilimoğlu, E. (2025). Xaminging revenge and forgiveness intentions in response to service failures: Insights from the hospitality industry. *Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 31(4). <https://doi.org/10.20867/thm.31.4.9>
- The Impact of Online Service Recovery Strategies on Perceived Justice and Customer Satisfaction: A Gender-Moderated Analysis. (2025). *Journal of Logistics Informatics and Service Science*. <https://doi.org/10.33168/jliss.2025.0417>
- Tirtayasa, S., Jufrizen, J., Pirari, W. S., & Sari, M. (2024). E-SATISFACTION AND E-LOYALTY: THE ROLE OF BRAND IMAGE AND E-SERVICE QUALITY. *EKUITAS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)*, 8(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.24034/j25485024.y2024.v8.i1.5677>
- Tseng, S. (2021). Understanding the impact of the relationship quality on customer loyalty: the moderating effect of online service recovery. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 13(2), 300–320. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijqss-07-2020-0115>
- Umar, R. M. (2022). Service recovery efforts' influence on consumers' desire to reciprocate and forgiveness: the mediating role of perceived justice. *South Asian Journal of Marketing*, 4(1), 74–91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/sajm-07-2022-0046>
- Utami, S. Y. R., Yulianto, E., & L.I.F, A. N. (2024). Beyond Convenience: Understanding E-Service Quality Role In Fostering E-Customer Satisfaction And Loyalty. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 28(2), 341–364.

- <https://doi.org/10.24912/jm.v28i2.1956>
- Wang, M., Sung, T. P., & Chekima, B. (2024). A Proposed Framework of E-Customer Satisfaction in China: E-Service Quality, Trust, Repurchase Intention. *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (MJSSH)*, 9(8). <https://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v9i8.2791>
- Wu, K. (2011). Customer Loyalty Explained by Electronic Recovery Service Quality: Implications of the Customer Relationship Re-Establishment for Consumer Electronics E-Tailers. *Contemporary Management Research*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.7903/cmr.1101>
- Yusnara, R. I., & Soepatini, S. (2023). Utilitarian, hedonic, and social values on e-commerce customer loyalty: mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Journal of Enterprise and Development*, 5(2), 296–316. <https://doi.org/10.20414/jed.v5i2.7009>
- Zhang, J., She, L., Wang, D., & Shafiq, A. (2022). Chinese Consumers' E-Learning Satisfaction and Continuance Purchase Intention on Paid Online Python Course. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.849627>
- Zhu, T., & Park, S. K. (2022). Encouraging Brand Evangelism Through Failure Attribution and Recovery Justice: The Moderating Role of Emotional Attachment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.877446>
- Zhu, T., Liu, B.-L., Song, M., & Wu, J. (2021). Effects of Service Recovery Expectation and Recovery Justice on Customer Citizenship Behavior in the E-Retailing Context. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.658153>